

ViableSite:

Unlocking the potential of small residential sites through AI automation

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

ViableSite

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Small sites with the potential for much-needed residential development are everywhere in the UK – yet many remain hidden, under-used or avoided because they're too costly and time-consuming to assess. As architect and [ViableSite](#) founder Kira Ariskina explains: "Even a seemingly small financial anomaly, like having to deal with unexpected underground utilities on site, can make or break not only a project, but an entire business." For SME developers, commissioning full teams to explore a site's feasibility is often economically impossible.

ViableSite was born out of Kira's years of experience assessing small sites in architecture practice and academia, and for Oxford City Council. Working across hundreds of plots, she saw how planning constraints, environmental factors, site-specific risks and sales potential all had to be manually gathered and interpreted – a process that was slow, expensive, fragmented, and dependent on a single expert to hold everything together. "I realised I was becoming a bottleneck," she says. "It was extremely lengthy, and it didn't make sense for smaller developers who have an auction in 24 hours' time and simply need to know: is this site viable, and should we buy it?"

With advances in AI, Kira saw an opportunity to automate major parts of the viability process by combining data from many different sources, including planning policy, geospatial information, utilities, environmental constraints, and sales data. She also envisaged a system in which sites could be matched with construction providers at the pre-acquisition stage based on bespoke sets of properties and constraints. But Kira needed to understand whether the idea was technically feasible, how to structure the system, and what data foundations were required.

That's when she discovered Innovate UK's BridgeAI Independent Scientific Advisor (ISA) offer, which paired ViableSite with Dr Ogerta Elezaj, Turing Fellow at The Alan Turing Institute and Associate Professor in Applied AI at Birmingham City University. Kira says: "I wrote the application and was successful – and we were extremely lucky to be paired with Ogerta. She's an absolute professional who understands construction and understands AI. Ogerta immediately drilled into my mind that AI is secondary – the quality of the data is the first priority and has to be collected in the proper fashion."

Since then, a significant part of Ogerta's input has focused on data ingestion. "The data comes in so many formats – PDF planning rules, geospatial layers, cost models, contractor datasets – and we used many of our ISA sessions to bring it all together into a unified repository," says Ogerta. "We now have a dataset in place where all these different sources are integrated, which means we can explore the use of deep-learning models to build the prediction system."

With Ogerta's support, ViableSite has moved from concept to the verge of a minimum viable product that will combine features including cloud-based visualisation of planning constraints, heatmaps of high-risk underground utility areas, predicted construction costs, natural language retrieval of key planning policies, and a human-in-the-loop element allowing architects to review the outputs of the AI 'agent' making the decisions. At the end, users will receive a clear go/no-go decision on whether they should develop the site – and an expected profit margin.

"Kira had a fantastic idea with substantial potential, but we were starting from the very beginning. Our first step was to build a clear AI strategy and roadmap – defining the problem, understanding the data landscape, and mapping how each component of the system should interact. Establishing the right foundation early on is essential for creating AI tools that are reliable and scalable."

Dr Ogerta Elezaj,

The Alan Turing Institute, Independent Scientific Advisor

Working together, Kira and Ogerta have also been successful in securing participation in the GeoAI Build and Pitch Programme, led by the UK government's Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), Innovate UK Business Connect, and partners. Access to the programme's datasets, cloud computing resource, and expert mentorship will allow ViableSite to integrate earth observation data into its workflow for the assessment of biodiversity net gain metrics and underground utilities risk.

As part of BridgeAI's support, Kira also attended a [BridgeAI Adopters and Developers networking event](#) hosted by the Turing. She says: "The event was amazing. I connected with so many people from the construction industry who were already further along in their AI journey, and they were incredibly open and generous with their insights – not just about AI development, but about building their businesses. For someone like me who's just starting out, it was genuinely encouraging and absolutely invaluable."

"Without this opportunity through BridgeAI – and without Ogerta – we wouldn't have been able to move this quickly. It's like having a very trustworthy friend who supports you through your decision-making and challenges your assumptions. In just two months, we've gone from an idea to being very close to a minimum viable product. The confidence Ogerta has given me is incredible, and I still can't believe how lucky we are to have this support."

Kira Ariskina
Founding Director, ViableSite

Credit: viablesite.co.uk

Now that ViableSite has collected and collated the relevant data, the team's next step is to begin training the models.

With around 600,000 available small sites across the UK, even unlocking a fraction could support SME developers, increase vital housing delivery, reduce costs for local authorities, and mitigate a range of risks in a challenging economic environment.

Kira Ariskina, Founding Director, ViableSite

“We already have the platform where all of this will sit, and we aim to be able to launch to a small number of customers in the first half of 2026. It's incredible how much has been achieved in just a few months.”

Kira Ariskina
Founding Director, ViableSite

Credit: viablesite.co.uk

About Innovate UK BridgeAI

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree and BSI.

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